

A Conical Cosmic Model: Unifying Dark Matter and Dark Energy

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Abstract

In this paper, we propose a new model of the universe based on a conical space-time fabric structure comprising seven layered folds. This model aims to provide a unified explanation for dark matter and dark energy as two manifestations of the same dynamic interaction in the spacetime fabric. We suggest that dark matter is a result of localized effects of folded layers enhancing gravitational density, while dark energy represents the forces arising from the expansion of these layers, driving the accelerated expansion of the universe. The idea is supported by initial mathematical formulations and observational predictions testable through Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) radiation and gravitational lensing effects.

1 Introduction

Dark matter and dark energy remain among the greatest mysteries in modern cosmology. Dark matter accounts for unexplained gravitational effects in galaxies, while dark energy is responsible for the accelerated expansion of the universe. The current standard model, Λ CDM, provides a robust framework but lacks a unified explanation for these phenomena.

In this paper, we propose a new model in which the universe is conceptualized as a conical spacetime fabric with seven layered folds. Each layer interacts dynamically with others, producing the effects we currently attribute to dark matter and dark energy.

2 Theoretical Model

2.1 Conical Spacetime Fabric Structure

We propose that the universe is structured as a conical spacetime fabric, consisting of seven interconnected layers centered around an origin point. Each layer of this spacetime fabric represents a distinct level of energy or gravitational density, dynamically interacting with adjacent layers to shape the observed cosmic phenomena. The localized curvatures within the fabric are hypothesized to account for the effects attributed to dark matter, while the outward expansion of the layers generates forces responsible for the observed accelerated expansion of the universe, interpreted as dark energy.

2.2 Dark Matter and Energy Effects

The localized effects of folded layers create increased gravitational densities, manifesting as dark matter. Meanwhile, the outward expansion of the layers generates forces responsible for the accelerated expansion, interpreted as dark energy.

3 Mathematical Formulation

The metric of the conical universe can be described as:

$$ds^2 = -c^2 dt^2 + a(t)^2 (dr^2 + r^2 d\theta^2 + f(r, \theta) dz^2) \quad (1)$$

where $f(r, \theta)$ represents the curvature introduced by the folded layers.

The modified Friedmann equation incorporating layer-induced energy density is given by:

$$H^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3}(\rho_{\text{matter}} + \rho_{\text{layers}}) - \frac{k}{a^2} + \frac{\Lambda}{3} \quad (2)$$

4 Observational Predictions

The proposed model makes several testable predictions:

- Distinct patterns in Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) radiation due to the curvature of the conical layers.
- Enhanced gravitational lensing effects caused by layer interactions.
- Variations in galaxy rotation curves consistent with localized gravitational densities.

5 Conclusion

This model provides a unified framework for understanding dark matter and dark energy as manifestations of the same underlying dynamic. By conceptualizing the universe as a conical spacetime fabric with layered folds, we open new avenues for both theoretical and observational exploration. Future work should focus on refining the mathematical framework and testing the predictions with empirical data.